

USING DIFFERENT METHODS IN TEACHING PRE INTERMEDIATE CLASS STUDENTS

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Abstract: The aim of this study is to investigate the effects of using Semantic Mapping Technique in comparison to traditional technique in vocabulary learning and to find out whether there is a relationship between students' beliefs about vocabulary learning strategies (VLSs) and what strategies they prefer to use. 32 students at the pre- intermediate level of English from Selcuk University, at the Department of School of Foreign Languages took part in the study. Quantitative data was collected through a two-part questionnaire. The results revealed that students' beliefs and their preferences were related. For the experimental study, target vocabulary items were taught with Semantic Mapping technique to experimental group and control group was introduced with traditional technique. To analyze the difference between semantic mapping technique and traditional technique, t-test calculations were used with the results of the pre-test and post-test. According to the results, semantic mapping technique is more effective than the traditional technique in vocabulary learning. (C) 2012 Published by Elsevier Ltd. Selection and/or peer-review under responsibility of ALSC 2012

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1.1 Method appropriate for young learners - TPR 1.1.1 Total Physical Response
TPR is an English teaching method developed by Dr. James J Asher whose aim is to draw learners' attention and encourage them to respond to the given commands. TPR teaches vocabulary by using psychomotor systems. Thanks to the combination of tracing and rehearsal activities the probability of receiving a successful effect in teaching rises. The method is believed to be perfect for teaching children and for using it as an additional technique during lessons "Ogromne sukcesy odnosi TPR w kursach dla dzieci. Znaczna jest też jej rola jako techniki pojedynczych ćwiczeń przeprowadzanych w środku lekcji wtedy, gdy uwaga uczniów spada i trzeba im dostarczyć nieco ruchu i hałasu." [TPR has been achieving great success in courses for children. Its role, as a technique of single activities used during the lesson when the students' attention decreases, and noise and movement are needed, is also significant.] (Komorowska, 2005:

30). – translated by Anna Peters. The method consists of coordination of two elements: speech and action. According to Asher, Total Physical Response is a natural way of teaching English. He claims that the naturalistic processes should be reflected in teaching the second language and learning. Three central processes are based on this idea: 1) the listening competence is developed before speaking ability. It means that children, at the early phase of first language acquisition, are able to understand complex utterances before they gain the ability to produce them. Creation of the mental „blueprint“ of the language, which was supposed to make spoken language production possible in the later phase of this listening, was taken into consideration by Asher. 2) “children’s ability in listening comprehension is acquired because children need to respond physically to spoken language in the form of parental commands; and” 3) “when a foundation in listening comprehension has been established, speech evolves naturally and effortlessly out of it” (Widodo, 2005: 237). According to Asher, to base the learning of foreign language upon the way in which children learn their native language is believed to be crucial (Widodo, 2005: 237).

1.1.2 Techniques Among the numerous techniques in Total Physical Response Method some of them are described: 1) Imperative drills are the major classroom activity in Total Physical Response. “They play an important role especially in eliciting the physical actions and activity on the part of the learners” (Richard et al. 1986: 92). According to Asher, an instructor can teach vocabulary and most of grammatical structures of the target language using the imperative (1997: 4). The target language is used communicatively from the beginning of instruction; students listen to the teacher. Students do not speak at first, but the teacher’s role is to help them to understand the point by showing pictures and occasionally using single words in children’s native language; being as expressive as possible is also acceptable and welcome. 2) When all children are ready to respond to comments, and they do it correctly, the next step is introduced – one of those children is asked to give instruction to other classmates. It is crucial to remember that children speak when they are ready to do it; they are not and must not be forced to do so. The level of anxiety in the classroom is reduced and thanks to it student’s self-confidence significantly rises. The creation of „low affective filter“ is considered to be the learning condition when the classroom is full of good atmosphere; “The filter is kept low as well by the fact that students are not put on the spot to speak” (Larsen-Freeman, 2000: 108). According to the following words, the absence of stress is really important in language acquisition “The learner is said to be liberated from

self-conscious and stressful situations and is able to devote full energy to learning” (Richard et al. 1986: 75). 3) Listening to tape-recorded words, phrases and sentences during looking at accompanying pictures is another technique in this method. It is the Winitz and Reed’s self-instructional program. The picture provides suitable context and because of it the meaning of the utterance is clear. Students are asked to respond to some questions by pointing at some pictures, but not using words. This exercise shows that they understand the language which they are listening; “Stories illustrated by pictures are also used as a device to convey abstract meaning” (Larsen-Freeman, 2000: 108). 4) The Lexical Approach, developed by Lewis, is more concerned with receiving comprehensible input and is less concerned with students’ production. It happens usually at lower levels when the teacher needs to talk extensively to the students and simultaneously do not get oral responses from them. The lexical exercises and activities are given to students to raise their awareness about lexical features about the target language. The phrasal lexicon of students can be developed by comprehensible input. Teachers talk abundantly to their students and simultaneously they do not require any responses from them. Thanks to the activities and exercises, which are given to the learners, students are encouraged to learn new phrases and notice lexical items. (Larsen-Freeman, 2000: 108). Komorowska (2005: 29-30) claims that “Metoda ta jest odpowiednia przede wszystkim dla zupełnie początkowych etapów nauczania. Jednak przy umiejętnym formułowaniu poleceń i stopniowym ich przedłużaniu można dojść do naprawdę skomplikowanych struktur gramatycznych. Na przykład: „Ania, zamknij okno! Marek, kiedy zobaczysz, że Ania już zamknęła okno – otwórz drzwi”, czy też „Jeśli okno zostało już zamknięte – otwórz drzwi, w przeciwnym razie zostaw je otwarte.” [This method is especially appropriate for completely early phases of teaching. However, there is a possibility to introduce, with the help of the skilful shaping of commands and progressive extend of them, really complicated grammar structures. For example: ‘Anna, close the window! Mark when you see Anna has already closed the window – open the door’ or ‘If the window has already been closed – open the door, if not, leave it open’. – translated by Anna Peters.

Direct Method The Direct Method is one of the oldest methods of teaching English. The main point of this method is not to use a native language. Teacher is not allowed to translate even a single word in students’ mother tongue. The target language is the only one which should be used in the classroom. What is more, the meaning is directly conveyed through visual aids and the

demonstrations. “Teachers must encourage direct and spontaneous use of the foreign language in the classroom” (Richard et al. 1986: 9). The teacher can use the already known words, mime, demonstrations and pictures to present or explain new vocabulary rather than teach using the analytical procedures, mostly based on explanation of grammar structures and rules. Grammar is presented inductively. That means that students are obliged to figure out the rules on their own using the presented examples; teacher can never give to the students an explicit grammar. Using new vocabulary and grammar structures is practiced in complete sentences. Nonetheless, all four skills (writing, reading, listening, speaking) occur from the beginning, speaking skill is emphasized over the rest of them. As far as the oral communication is concerned, teaching vocabulary is really important (Larsen-Freeman, 2000: 29). According to Komorowska, this method is considered to be suitable for adolescents because they usually value dynamic interactive activities, which are typical of communicative approach, however, they also accept entertaining elements of TPR and the naturalness of the Direct Method. (Komorowska, 2005: 35)

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